

MODULAR TECHNOLOGY FOR TEACHING STUDENTS IN THE SCIENCE OF FORENSIC MEDICINE

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In modern conditions of development of society, the requirements for the level of training of personnel are increasing. Before Higher education is faced with the task of preparing a competitive specialist with professional competence, mobility, readiness for constant updating of knowledge and skills, as well as the ability to apply the acquired knowledge for the successful solution of professional tasks. Taking into account that in the process of studying the effectiveness of education, it is determined by the degree to which the student actively participates in the learning process, new teaching methods and forms should create an opportunity for students to participate in the process of independent thinking and creative work. Today, innovative pedagogical technologies of education are used not only in foreign countries, but also in higher education institutions in our Republic. Among the modern pedagogical technologies, the main attention in monitoring the knowledge of students and improving the learning process is focused on the system of module learning.

Currently, the main goal of higher education is to form and develop the personal creativity of future specialists, to acquire independent knowledge, to increase innovative activities, to improve modern medical sciences, and to acquire broad clinical thinking and practical skills. The length of a modular sleeper is called a sleeper module. The term module (in Latin "modulies" or "modulus" - size and method) entered the pedagogical process from computer science. The study module is a collection of study methods and all the necessary information for studying a set of specific subjects. The module system allows the student to improve the subject and monitor the level of knowledge at the same time. The modular heating process is fundamentally different from traditional heating methods. At the end of each module, students will be assessed as usual by submitting a final examination, and their number will increase compared to the traditional system of evaluation. It is an element of the modular system, which includes the evaluation of students' knowledge according to the rating system and the identification of the results of the students' knowledge gained from each module by means of passing points. There are a number of advantages of modular sleeping. All students acquire all study materials at the same rate without postponing them to the last deadline. X, each completed module, tests worked by the student, situational problems, practical skills, and at the same time, the results

of the student's accumulated work on the module are evaluated (the completion of homework, the student's activity in practical classes, abstracts and other scientific works of the student are also taken into account). The student works independently for many hours and learns independent planning, organization, self-monitoring, and self-evaluation. The student understands himself as a person, independently determines the level of his knowledge, learns the shallow aspects of his knowledge and skills. The modular system of education contributes to improving the quality of trainees' training both in theoretical and practical aspects of education; providing high motivation for the learning process; changes and the acquisition by students of confidence in their abilities. Thus, the module acts as a means of modular training, as it includes: a target action plan, an information bank, a methodological guide for achieving goals. It is the modular system that can act as a training program that allows each student to achieve better results in educational activities, promotes self-development, creates a need for additional cognitive work and an increase in the level of knowledge among students, individualized in content, teaching methods, level of independence, pace of educational and cognitive student activities. In conclusion, it should be said that the use of modular teaching in the Bukhara Medical Institute increases the efficiency and activity of students' education, helps to strengthen their professional knowledge, helps them to acquire high-level training of future medical specialists, wide-ranging clinical thinking and practical skills, meets educational standards. responds and guarantees a high level of education.

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